

D8.5

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Report:

Our Journey Toward a Paradigm Shift in Multi-Hazard Risk Assessment and Management

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D8.5/MYRIAD-EU Final report: Our Journey Toward a Paradigm Shift in Multi- Hazard Risk Assessment and Management

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Abstract

MYRIAD-EU is a Horizon 2020 project that has a vision to catalyse the paradigm shift required to move towards a multi-risk, multi-sector, systemic approach to risk assessment and management. Its overall aim is that by the end of MYRIAD-EU policy-makers, decision-makers, and practitioners will be able to develop forward-looking disaster risk management pathways that assess trade-offs and synergies across sectors, hazards, and scales.

To achieve this, MYRIAD-EU developed a harmonised framework, data resources, modelling tools, and decision-support approaches for forward-looking disaster risk management. These outputs were co-developed and tested through five Pilot case study regions (North Sea, Canary Islands, Scandinavia, Danube, Veneto), in close collaboration with stakeholders from six key sectors (Finance, Infrastructure & Transport, Food & Agriculture, Ecosystems & Forestry, Tourism, and Energy). Throughout the project, Early Career Researchers played a central role, contributing substantially to scientific innovation and project legacy.

This final report synthesises the main outcomes of MYRIAD-EU, bringing together results from the core scientific work packages, insights from the Pilots and sectors, and lessons for future research and practice in managing multi-risks.

Dissemination level of the document

- Public
- Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
- Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the European Commission Services)
- Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the European Commission Services)

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1 Introduction

Hazards rarely occur in isolation, often one hazard triggers another (for example, rainfall leading to flooding), and the likelihood of a subsequent hazardous event can be amplified by a prior one (such as drought increasing wildfire risk). These interconnected or cascading events, collectively referred to as multi-hazards, significantly influence overall risk. Multi-risk occurs when multiple hazards interact with dynamic changes in exposure (i.e., the people, infrastructure, housing, and other elements located in hazard-prone areas) and vulnerability (i.e., the susceptibility of those exposed elements to the impacts of hazards). Consequently, analyses that consider hazards individually often underestimate total risk, as interactions between hazards, and their exposure and vulnerability, can produce impacts that differ substantially from the simple sum of their independent effects. Therefore, a paradigm shift is required to move towards a multi-risk, multi-sector, systemic approach to risk assessment and management (Ward et al., 2022).

The MYRIAD-EU project, funded under Horizon 2020, aimed to catalyse this paradigm shift in disaster risk management (DRM). Its vision was that, by the end of the project, policymakers, decision-makers, and practitioners would be equipped to develop forward-looking DRM pathways. MYRIAD-EU pursued this vision through eight Work Packages (WPs) (see Figure 1). At the start, WP1 focused on diagnosis, developing a common baseline and shared understanding of multi-hazard and multi-risk definitions, indicators, functions, methods, tools, and policies. Building on this, WP2 co-designed a harmonised framework for multi-hazard, multi-sector, and systemic risk management. At the core of MYRIAD-EU was WP3, which co-developed forward-looking DRM pathways in five case study areas (Pilots) by iteratively testing and updating the framework. The Pilots were informed by the three thematic WPs; WP4 to WP6. WP4 created an online catalogue of data, algorithms, and methods to empirically assess the dynamics and feedback of risk drivers. WP5 developed software tools for generating both quantitative and qualitative multi-hazard and multi-risk scenarios. WP6 focused on decision support, developing approaches to help risk managers, decision-makers, and policymakers navigate the complexities of risk-informed, forward-looking decision-making. WP7 oversaw communication and dissemination of results, while WP8 was responsible for project management and coordination.

An integral component of MYRIAD-EU was the involvement of sectoral representatives, who ensured the scientific work remained relevant, facilitated engagement with key stakeholders, and supported dissemination within their sectors while contributing to the Pilot regions. These sectors were Finance, Infrastructure & Transport, Food & Agriculture, Ecosystems & Forestry, Tourism, and Energy.

Another core aspect of the project was the central role played by Early Career Researchers (ECRs). ECRs made up ~30% of the consortium, and ECR empowerment was a core focus of the project from the proposal phase right up until the legacy phase.

Throughout MYRIAD-EU, progress and results were extensively documented in project deliverables and peer-reviewed publications. In this report, we synthesise the main outcomes by bringing together the key outputs and findings in one place. We first present the main results from Work Packages 1 to 6, followed by an overview of sectoral impacts and recommendations, impacts of early career researchers, and an outlook for future work.

While this report provides a concise summary of the project's achievements, it does not attempt to capture the full depth of analysis undertaken across the consortium. Readers interested in further detail can refer to the individual deliverables and scientific papers produced within the project, which provide comprehensive descriptions of the methodologies, analyses, and results. A full scientific synthesis paper has also been developed as a legacy of the project (Ward et al., 2025).

2 Key outcomes per Work Package

In this section we highlight the main outputs of Work Packages 1 to 6. First, we discuss Work Packages 1 and 2, as they lay the foundations for the subsequent work in the project through the development of common definitions and a harmonised framework. This is followed by an overview of Work Packages 4 to 6, referred to as the thematic Work Packages. Finally, we present the forward-looking DRM pathways and background analyses developed in Work Package 3 (the Pilot regions).

Figure 1: Overview of Work Package (WP) structure. WP Leaders shown in bold and WP co-leads shown in italics. An overview of institute acronyms is provided in Appendix 1

2.1 WP1 Diagnosis

WP1 aimed to provide a common baseline understanding of multi-hazard terminology, concepts, methods and policies on multi-hazard risk assessment and management. As there were partners from different countries and disciplines involved in MYRIAD-EU, WP1 aimed to develop a common understanding of terminology and concepts related to multi-risk. To achieve this common baseline early on in the project D1.2, the Handbook of Multi-hazard, Multi-Risk Definitions and Concepts, was published in the first year of the project (Gill et al., 2022). The creation of the handbook included contributions from partners across the consortium. 140 terms are included in the handbook, 102 related to multi-hazard, multi-risk, disaster risk management and an additional 38 due to their relevance to the project. Definitions were obtained from established literature and experts within the project. The Handbook has been adopted by other multi-hazard risk projects (e.g. EO4MULTIHAZARDS, MEDiate), showcasing its value as a resource and its contribution to establishing a common language for multi-hazard and multi-risk research.

To complement the Handbook on definitions, WP1 developed a wiki-style online crowdsourcing platform, named the Disaster Risk Gateway (https://disasterriskgateway.net/index.php/Main_Page) (D1.1, Duncan et al., 2022). The Disaster

Risk Gateway provides all the definitions listed in the Handbook, and its online, interactive nature enables opportunities for updating these definitions as they may evolve through time. Additionally, there is a catalogue containing examples of frameworks, platforms, methods, models and tools for multi-hazard risk assessment and management. The catalogue was underpinned by existing reviews of multi-hazard risk approaches and initially populated by members of the MYRIAD-EU consortium and other professionals during a series of 'Wikithons', collaborative events where participants contributed new content to the Disaster Risk Gateway based on their expertise. To continue expanding the catalogue, anyone with expertise in multi-hazard risk can contribute by creating or editing pages after registering for a user account. The Disaster Risk Gateway is a valuable resource for researchers, policymakers, and other professionals, providing clear and well-structured access to multi-risk definitions, tools, and methods all in one place, and also includes contributions from outside the MYRIAD-EU project.

WP1 also carried out a review of policies, policy-making processes, and governance for multi-hazard, multi-risk management in the EU, providing an overview of current practices, sectoral dependencies, and guidelines for navigating multi-sector risk (D1.3, Schlumberger et al., 2022a). The report provides an overview of the governance landscape for managing multi-risks, highlighting guidelines, good practices, conceptual developments, barriers, and opportunities. The analysis draws on internal consultations, literature review, and stakeholder interviews. Although multi-risk governance is increasingly recognised, systematic implementation remains limited. As of 2022, National Risk Assessments (NRAs) remain the primary tool for DRM governance, with notable differences across countries. The literature review and interviews confirm that operational multi-risk approaches are still in their infancy, despite calls for paradigm shifts. The report concludes with recommendations: moving from conceptual frameworks to operational tools, integrating multi-risk processes, leveraging existing knowledge, engaging in collaborative initiatives, and embedding multi-risk governance in long-term strategies. These steps are essential for transitioning toward effective, systemic multi-risk governance in Europe.

Building on this research, the MYRIAD-EU consortium played a key role in bringing the multi-risk concept into the update of the UNDRR/International Science Council Hazard Information Profiles (HIPs) (UNDRR/ISC, 2025). In close consultation with UNDRR/ISC, the MYRIAD-EU Consortium developed a concept note (Gill et al., 2025) that supported the development of the HIPs update. The concept note brings together and synthesises a rich body of research, scholarship, and conceptual reviews to advance understanding of the multi-hazard concept. It particularly focuses on the relevance of interrelationships that exist between different hazard types to diverse users of the HIPs. It argues that deepening this understanding of the multi-hazard concept, and applying it in the context of the HIPs, is critical for addressing the improvements called for in the 2023 Political Declaration of the High-Level Meeting on the Midterm Review of the Sendai Framework, and for supporting the full implementation of the Sendai Framework and successor frameworks.

2.2 WP2 Framework & Synthesis

WP2 aimed to co-develop a harmonised framework for multi-hazard, multi-sector, systemic risk management. The initial framework was co-developed early on in the project and was based on existing literature and co-production with MYRIAD-EU partners and external experts. In April, 2022, a hybrid workshop was organised at the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA) in Laxenburg, Austria, to evaluate a prototype of the framework. Here, feedback was gathered from MYRIAD-EU participants, sectoral representatives and experts from the field (D2.1, Hochrainer-Stigler et al., 2022). The framework was then elaborated and published as a scientific paper by Hochrainer-Stigler et al. (2023).

The framework consists of 6 steps (Figure 2) to guide the user through managing and analysing multi-hazard risk:

- **Finding a system definition:** at the start of the framework the user needs to understand the system under consideration, as well as the system boundaries, such as the geographic location, sectors involved, policies in place, and hazards of interest.

- **Characterisation of direct risk:** determining the direct risks present in the system based on the relevant risk metrics. For example displaced population from specific hazards, or number of casualties.
- **Characterisation of indirect risk:** Indirect risk refers to the cascading risks and losses that arise through system interdependencies after direct risk has occurred. For example a supply chain disruption because critical infrastructure has been damaged.
- **Evaluation of direct and indirect risk:** based on the identified direct and indirect risk, the risks that need to be managed are selected. This phase facilitates decision-making between stakeholders to prioritise which risks require management, recognising that limited resources and competing priorities mean not all direct or indirect risks can be addressed.
- **Defining risk management options:** Based on the risk identification, different risk managements are evaluated. Management options need to consider different time horizons and, in a multi-hazard setting, synergies and synergies across options.
- **Accounting for future system states:** This step accounts for changes in risk components driven by large processes (e.g., climate, demographic, political, land use) and by the implementation of risk management measures. As these processes alter system boundaries and elements at risk, both direct and indirect risks must be re-evaluated, along with the effectiveness of proposed management options in future system states.

Figure 2: The MYRIAD-EU multi-risk Framework (adapted from Hochrainer-Stigler et al., 2023)

The different steps of the Framework are featured on an online dashboard (<https://dashboard.myriadproject.eu/>) to help users to develop forward looking disaster risk management plans (D2.3, Brookes et al., 2025). For each step of the framework, the dashboard provides different tools and methods developed in the thematic work packages of MYRIAD-EU that can support the execution of that step. A follow-on paper based on the original framework (Hochrainer-Stigler et al. 2023) is currently under review (Hochrainer-Stigler et al., 2025), which presents the final framework, guidance protocols and experiences made during the implementation process in the Pilots.

2.3 WP4 Dynamic Feedback between Risk Drivers

Within and amongst multi-hazard events there are several dynamics that influence the risk. In a perspective paper carried out as part of the project, de Ruiter and Van Loon (2022) argue that vulnerability can be dynamic if: (1) a hazard makes a population more vulnerable to a subsequent hazard; and/or (2) the implementation of disaster risk reduction (DRR) measures aimed at addressing these hazards changes the vulnerability to those hazards. In order to understand these dynamic feedback between risk drivers, WP4 built an online database to improve our understanding of dynamic feedbacks between risk drivers and by populating that database with novel methods to represent these dynamics in risk models.

Throughout MYRIAD-EU there have been many methods developed, data collected and analyses conducted. These and other methods are featured in the Metadatabase for Dynamics of Risk Drivers (<https://zenodo.org/records/15553940>) (D4.5, Stolte et al., 2025a, 2025b). The Metadatabase is intended for use by scientists and practitioners in the field of disaster risk modelling, offering comprehensive metadata attributes and associated references. Selected methods and datasets contained within the database are listed and described below:

1. We developed an algorithm that identifies multi-hazard events from the Emergency Events Database EM-DAT, based on information on associated hazards and spatiotemporal overlap. The impacts of the multi-hazard events were statistically compared against impacts from individual hazards to assess potential risk dynamics (Jäger et al., 2025). This shows that multi-hazards have a substantial share in the overall impacts of natural hazards around the globe.
2. We used DBSCAN (Density Based Spatial Clustering Application with Noise) to extract dynamic multi-hazard spatiotemporal footprints. The footprints of multi-hazard events were used to extract information on the single and multi-hazard event duration, intensity, extent, and seasonality under current and future climate conditions (Ferrario et al., 2025a). This allowed us to evaluate multi-hazard hotspots and potential future hazard combinations that were not observed in the past.
3. We developed a global framework for multi-hazard susceptibility and applied it to Japan (Tiggeloven et al., 2025), and the Veneto region (Ferrario et al., 2025b). These susceptibility maps show spatial representations of the likelihood of specific hazards (such as landslides or floods) occurring in different geographic areas, trained by advanced machine learning methods on historical hazard-influencing factors such as topography, geology, hydrology, land use, and vegetation.
4. We applied machine-learning approaches to assess coastal hazard interactions and project future extreme-event risks (Dal Barco et al., 2024, 2025).
5. We investigated hazards and impact by looking at the relevant impact duration of heatwaves (De Polt et al., 2023). De Polt et al., (2025) expands further on this in a study that shows that identical hazard intensities can produce different impacts depending on multi-hazard conditions.
6. We showed that vulnerability to multi-(hazard)-risk is unequally distributed around the world, with socioeconomic conditions, such as human development index, political stability, and distance to healthcare, playing a critical role (Tiggeloven et al., 2025a)
7. We explored Vulnerability drivers in *VulneraCity*, an urban vulnerability drivers database, in which drivers are categorised
8. We investigated what different methods are used to assess such vulnerability drivers, specifically in the context of flooding (Schlumberger & Stolte et al., 2025)
9. We explored how dynamic exposure and vulnerability conditions following a first disaster can significantly influence people's ability to respond and recover from subsequent events (Buijs et al., 2025). The precise impact on the recovery duration of a multi-hazard event vs. a single-hazard event is investigated in a novel study using nighttime light satellite data (Buijs et al., forthcoming)

- We conducted stakeholder interviews in the Pilot regions (van Maanen et al., 2025). These interviews generated crucial insights that informed the forward-looking DRM pathways developed for those regions. They also underscored the need to adopt vulnerability assessment and management approaches that are explicitly tailored to evolving local conditions, hazard-specific dynamics, and emerging risk contexts.

The Metadatabase is intended to be a living document, expanding with new entries over time. As it grows, we gain progressive insights that help us refine and improve its structure. Beyond MYRIAD-EU, we aim to embed the metadatabase in future proposals on dynamic risks, with the goal of securing funding to support its continued development and to integrate it into the Disaster Risk Gateway.

2.4 WP5 Multi-Risk Scenarios

The aim of WP5 was to develop methods and user-friendly software to generate realistic multi-hazard and multi-risk event sets that include future climate and socioeconomic scenarios and different hazard interrelationships (D5.4, Daniell et al., 2025). To achieve this, first different methods to generate hazard event sets and quantifying risk have been developed.

Early discussions with stakeholders in the Pilots within MYRIAD-EU revealed that the understanding of current multi-hazard events remains very limited, with no widely applicable event sets beyond case studies. To address this gap, we developed the MYRIAD-Hazard Event Set Algorithm (MYRIAD-HESA) (Claassen et al., 2023), which compiles single-hazard footprints into multi-hazard event sets based on their spatial and temporal overlap. Using eleven hazard types, we created the first global multi-hazard event set database, enabling the identification of hotspots, frequent hazard pairs such as heatwave-drought and cyclone-flood (see Figure 3), and more complex groups like multiple earthquakes followed by tsunamis and landslides.

Figure 3: The most frequent hazard pairs globally (Claassen et al., 2023)

MYRIAD-HESA shows us what has happened in the past, however, methods are also required to evaluate what could happen in the future. Within MYRIAD-EU this is achieved through the use of stochastic data and storylines. Stochastic data provide plausible events based on the statistical properties of historic observations. Within MYRIAD-EU, we developed a stochastic earthquake set for Europe (Schaefer et al., 2022). We also developed MYRIAD-SIM, a weather generator that simulates extreme variables while preserving their dependencies using *VineCopulas*, an open-source Python package (Claassen et al., 2024, 2025). MYRIAD-SIM was used to evaluate the likelihood of high impact multi-hazard extreme weather events, such as the occurrence of multiple storms in close succession. The results show that while some multi-hazard events are rare, they

may reach higher intensities than those observed historically, meaning they may pose greater risks than suggested by past records alone.

Within WP5 (D5.3, Daniell et al., 2024), we also studied indirect impacts, such as disrupted supply chains that cause economic losses for businesses outside the hazard zone, and showed that indirect impacts strongly affect the overall impacts of hazard events by evaluating common sets of hazard events across macro-economic models (IIASA-ABM, GRACE, MRIA). Through the examination of specific scenarios like the Danube region's earthquake and flood events, we demonstrate that indirect impacts can influence regional and sectoral economies in ways not immediately apparent from direct damage assessments alone. Our results reveal that regions not directly affected by a hazard event can both benefit from shifting demand and increased economic activity due to reconstruction efforts as well as suffer from missing inputs produced in affected regions. However, the magnitude of both indirect and total impacts varies strongly across modelling approaches. This variability can lead to divergent estimates of the economic implications of hazards, reflecting fundamental differences in their underlying assumptions, data inputs, and methodological frameworks.

To complement the varying modelling approaches and make multi-hazard scenarios more accessible to a broader audience, a user-friendly online software has been developed (<https://www.myriad-multirisk.eu/>). The MYRIAD-EU Software combines a range of different data into one place, such as vulnerability curves for different hazards, and both current and future hazard exposure data in the exposure at risk explorer. The different functionalities are further explained in D5.4 (Daniell et al., 2025). A key learning from the development of multi-hazard scenarios was that different sectors require different risk metrics. Therefore, the software provides multiple exposure indicators such as GDP, population, and tourism expenditure, allowing sector-specific assessment of multi-hazard risks. The software is open-source, available online for anyone to use, and will continue to be maintained, tested, and further developed beyond the end of the project.

2.5 WP6 Risk Informed Decision Making

Decision making for adaptation strategies and DRM for multi-risk can be a complex task as there are many stakeholders involved within a system. Within WP6 differences in the effectiveness of DRM options between single and multi-hazards, and trade-offs and synergies between hazards, sectors, regions, and decision and policy goals, have been explored. As a first step, an extensive literature review was conducted to identify promising tools and approaches for collaborative system analysis which could be applied in the MYRIAD-EU Pilots. These tools and approaches are explored in D6.2 (Warren et al., 2023).

One of the main methods that was developed to guide the Pilots to make forward-looking DRM decisions is DAPP-MR (Dynamic Adaptive Policy Pathways for Multi-Risk), which is a multi-risk extension of the original DAPP. Adaptation pathways are “A series of adaptation choices involving trade-offs between short-term and long-term goals and values. These are processes of deliberation to identify solutions that are meaningful to people in the context of their daily lives and to avoid potential maladaptation.” (IPCC, 2022). Within the multi-risk context, DAPP-MR aims to develop different pathways that consider different future sectors and hazards, as well as the interactions between them. DAPP-MR considers three key themes relevant to the design of multi-risk DRM pathways: (1) the effects of multiple, interacting hazards; (2) the dynamics and interdependencies of sectors; and (3) the trade-offs and synergies of DRM policy options across different sectors and different spatial and temporal scales. It does so by proposing three, iterative stages of the first four steps of the DAPP policy analysis cycle to gradually build up problem complexity. These stages and steps are provided in Figure 4 and further highlighted in Schlumberger et al. (2022b).

Figure 4: The different steps of Dynamic Adaptive Policy Pathways for Multi-Risk (DAPP-MR) (Schlumberger et al., 2022b)

The utility of DAPP-MR was tested using a synthetic test case (Schlumberger et al., 2024) and in the Pilot regions (Schlumberger et al., 2025b). Additionally, in order to make DAPP-MR more accessible to decision makers, a visual analytics dashboard prototype was designed to support pathways analysis for multi-risk Disaster Risk Management (DRM) (Schlumberger, 2025c). The pathways analysis dashboard employs interactive visualisations of pathways and their evaluation – including Decision Trees, Parallel Coordinates Plots, Stacked Bar Charts, Heatmaps, and Pathways Maps – to facilitate complex, multi-criteria decision-making under uncertainty (Schlumberger, 2025c).

Beyond DAPP-MR and collaborative systems analysis, MYRIAD-EU has explored the application of multi-(hazard)-risk storylines to support risk-informed decision-making within the Pilot regions. MYRIAD-EU has developed a storylines approach to explore cause-and-effect relationships in a multi-risk system(s) (Crummy et al., 2025). Storylines enable a holistic examination of cascading effects, critical thresholds, and emerging risks, all of which are essential for improved understanding and decision-making in complex multi-(hazard)-risk environments (Cocuccioni et al., 2025).

The MYRIAD-EU multi-(hazard)-risk storyline approach uses guiding questions, throughout 5 stages, to break down the complexity and examine the interacting nature of multi-risk systems through analysis of past or plausible future events (see Figure 5). Currently four different storylines, in the MYRIAD-EU Pilot regions, are available on the MYRIAD-EU online repository of storylines (<https://dashboard.myriadproject.eu/storylines-repository/>) (D6.5, Crummy et al., 2025):

- 1953 North Sea Floods
- Future Climate implications on the North Sea
- Storm Vaia 2018 – Vaia 2.0, Veneto Region
- Heatwave, drought and forest fire, Scandinavia

As of November 2025 another one is under development:

- Tourism Resilience under Multi-Hazard cascading Risks: Insights from La Palma 2021 (title TBC)

Figure 5: The five stages to develop multi-risk storylines (D6.5, Crummy et al., 2025)

2.6 WP3 Pilots

Within MYRIAD-EU, the Framework for multi-hazard, multi-sector, systemic risk management developed in WP2 and the tools and methods developed in the thematic WPs 4-6 were tested in five Pilot regions (Figure 6) in collaboration with relevant stakeholders. The Pilots were selected based on their distinct geographical features, exposure to a variety of hazards, and socio-economic challenges. Each Pilot followed a stepwise, knowledge co-production process to characterise their multi-risk profile and develop tailored forward-looking DRM pathways across relevant hazards and sectors (Gottardo et al., 2025).

Figure 6: The five MYRIAD-EU Pilot regions

This process was facilitated through workshops, focus groups, and interviews with local stakeholders (van Maanen et al., 2025; Ciurean et al., 2025). Four Pilots used the DAPP-MR approach to develop pathways (Schlumberger et al., 2025b). In the Veneto Pilot, the UCPM PRAF (Union Civil Protection Mechanism Peer Review Assessment Framework) guided the development of governance-focused pathways (Mysiak et al., 2021; Casartelli et al., 2025a). In each Pilot, the pathways addressed a set of relevant hazards and sectors as well as their interrelationships and were informed by the results generated from the testing of a mix of qualitative (e.g., storylines) and quantitative (e.g., AI-based) tools. Results are illustrated in detail in D3.4 (Gottardo et al., 2025) and briefly summarized in the subsections below.

2.6.1 North Sea Pilot

The North Sea Pilot focussed on balancing competing interest in spatial planning at sea and on the coast under the increasing pressure of interrelated risk, driven by extreme wind, storms, heat, lightning, precipitation, fog and coastal flooding. The sectors that are exposed to these risks and were evaluated within this Pilot are:

- Energy
- Shipping
- Nature conservation

Within the North Sea Pilot, DAPP-MR was applied to develop forward-looking DRM pathways addressing these sectors individually as well as their interrelationships and trade-offs. The North Sea is an interesting case to evaluate as it is currently undergoing changes to reach renewable energy targets (e.g., through wind farms and cables), while at the same time meeting marine regulations (e.g., fishing zones, marine protected areas) and increasing maritime transport needs. This creates not only a space issue on the North Sea, but also generates more exposure to increasing risks, such as storms, which may damage infrastructure or cause ship collisions.

Each sector defined a set of goals, for which corresponding adaptation measures were identified. For example, the nature sector focused on the goal of achieving a good ecological status. To achieve this, measures like combating invasive species and wastewater management were selected. Likewise, the energy sector established the goals of maximising energy production and minimising

downtime of wind farms. The shipping sector identified goals that emphasise continuous future growth of the sector, while maintaining commitments to safety. Each of these goals, along with their associated set of measures, was then evaluated and combined across sectors. For example, a multi-sector pathway focussing on Nature Enhancement, Offshore Wind Expansion, and Surveillance & Windfarms could be pursued simultaneously.

The DRM pathways developed in the North Sea Pilot are a starting point for multi-risk thinking in an offshore context, and will be leveraged in follow-up projects. In future work, the pathways developed in the North Sea Pilot will be further refined in the national research project ECOAMARE (Ecosystem-based Adaptive Management for Renewable Energy in a Sustainable North Sea).

2.6.2 Canary Island Pilot

The Canary Island Pilot faces many vulnerabilities that are typical for remote island regions, such as a dependency on international tourism, scarce natural resources (e.g. water, land), reliance on external resources and persistent inequality. At the same time the Canary Islands are exposed to multiple interacting hazards such as droughts, heatwaves, wildfires, flash/compound coastal floods, sea-level rise, and volcanic eruptions. To manage these multi-risks, DAPP-MR was applied to the La Palma island for the following sectors:

- Food and agriculture
- Tourism

We modelled water as the cross-sector coordinating budget for pathway design. Energy was represented solely as a boundary condition for operational continuity, reflecting that La Palma's potable supply relies on groundwater rather than energy-intensive desalination. With water risk decoupled from electricity, the system is less exposed to grid outages but more exposed to failures in subsurface capture and irrigation networks, including blockages, ash-rain interactions, landslides, and volcanic gas contamination of aquifers, as well as to aquifer depletion and governance fragmentation.

On La Palma, the 2021 Cumbre Vieja eruption exposed how risks cascaded across different sectors. Agriculture suffered through the destruction of cropland by lava flows, while tourism experienced a setback due to, amongst other factors, reduced accommodation capacity and, consequently, air travel connectivity. In light of this disaster, whose impacts were investigated through a dedicated Storyline, La Palma served as a blueprint for the DAPP-MR analysis within island contexts.

Quantitative pathways were developed for each sector based on a specific objective that aligned with the island development and recovery goals. Food and agriculture, focused on enhancing water-use efficiency for the subsidised banana production and reducing its vulnerability to droughts and market disruptions for which adaptation measures like expanding greenhouses and increasing irrigation efficiency are considered. Tourism aimed to rebuild and expand accommodation capacity while increasing resource efficiency, particularly in water consumption, for which adaptation measures like the development of eco-lodges and installing water efficient devices were proposed. The interaction between the different sectors were considered by their shared water demand and the projected available water under future drought and heatwave conditions.

The findings of the Canary Islands Pilot will be integrated into AQUAMAN (Interreg Euro-MED), a programme that will co-create, test, and upscale water-efficiency solutions through seven Living Labs on Mediterranean islands, with additional Atlantic Living Labs in Portugal and Spain, and with the Canary Islands Living Lab led by the University of La Laguna (ULL). This will ensure that strategic foresights are not left as an academic exercise but are directly translated into operational experimentation.

2.6.3 Scandinavia Pilot

Scandinavia is increasingly prone to multi-hazards such as combinations of heatwaves, droughts, and wildfires, which had widespread cross-sectoral impacts across the region in 2018. This event was documented and analysed in a dedicated Storyline by Crummy et al., (2025) and an economic

analysis by Ducros et al. (2025). Within this context, the Scandinavia Pilot developed future pathways applying DAPP-MR specifically to Norway, focusing on the energy sector in connection with two other sectors. Norway is mostly self-sufficient in electricity generation, with 90% of the electricity being generated by hydropower. Hydropower is a renewable energy source, making it a key driver towards a more sustainable future. However, the sector faces an increasing exposure to extreme events and multi-hazards. Combined natural hazards such as heatwave, drought, extreme precipitation, and flooding can all cause significant fluctuations in hydropower inflows. Periods with too little water may reduce electricity production, while excessive water inflow can decrease production efficiency and lead to wasted hydropower generation. Therefore, the Scandinavia Pilot focussed specifically on the energy sector, while investigating its relationships with two other sectors, food and agriculture as well as ecosystems and forestry.

In this work, the Pilot considered that the main goal of the Norwegian energy sector is to build a more resilient and sustainable system in response to growing climate variability and evolving societal needs. Hence, many of the proposed measures focus on alternative energy sources, such as bioenergy, and offshore wind. These measures were evaluated against the following six dimensions:

- Social acceptance
- Impacts on nature and ecosystems
- Energy security
- Economic profitability
- Resilience to climate shocks, including multi-hazards
- Cross-sectoral interactions, focusing on agriculture and forestry

Cross-sectoral interactions focus on synergies and trade-offs with the agriculture and forestry sectors. For example, the development of onshore wind may have a negative impact on agriculture and forestry because of spatial requirements, thereby showing that different measures have varying impacts on the relevant sectors and more cross-sectoral coordination is required. The resilience to climate shocks such as multi-hazards may be more feasible at a local scale. This was explored throughout a side project with the municipality of Bergen focusing on climate risks from multi-hazards for the municipal area, where stakeholders confirmed the value of focussing on a local context. In the future the Pilot has the ambition to continue local multi-risk assessments across Norway and Northern Europe.

2.6.4 Danube Pilot

The Danube Pilot had a strong focus on the cross boundary economic ties between neighbouring countries, with a special focus on the impacts of floods, earthquakes and droughts with regard to the following sectors:

- Transport
- Finance

For each sector, drivers of future change, causal relationships with droughts and floods, objectives, and potential responses were identified. For example, one of the drivers for future change in the agriculture sector is 'maintaining levels of agricultural production'. A causal relationship between this and hazards is that floods and droughts may destroy yields which leads to decreased production and which can, as a further consequence, result in economic losses. An objective for the sector is to minimise crop losses, for which a measure is better water management.

Based on the sectoral analysis detailed above, future climate scenarios for the region and potential DRM measures for each sector, DRM pathways were drafted using DAPP-MR to achieve the individual sectors' short-term to long-term goals. In the Final Pilot Workshop in 2025, the single-sector pathways for agriculture and navigation were used as a basis to develop cross-sectoral

pathways through co-creation. These pathways feature some measures required to meet the sector goals, such as implementing early warning systems and flood-proofing infrastructure, as well as enabling conditions to successfully coordinate DRM measures across sectors.

The stakeholder relationships developed during the project are strong, and have already led to offers to present results at steering group meetings of key organisations, as well as opportunities to contribute to upcoming updates of regional management strategies. In particular, the Pilot team is contributing to the update of the Danube River Basin Management Plan, expected in 2027, where the systemic and cross-border perspective applied in MYRIAD-EU supports efforts to strengthen regional cooperation on climate resilience.

2.6.5 Veneto Pilot

The Veneto Pilot explored compound climate risks across its diverse landscapes, including coastal zones prone to flooding, agricultural plains prone to droughts and mountain areas prone to landslides. To identify current and future key risks and hotspots in these areas a mix-method approach was used combining AI-based tools (Dal Barco et al., 2025; Ferrario et al., 2024; Ferrario et al., 2025b) with qualitative tools such as multi-risk Storylines (Casartelli et al. 2025b; Casartelli et al., submitted). The Veneto Pilot used the Union Civil Protection Mechanism (UCPM) PRAF to develop general multi-risk pathways and tailored cross-sectoral DRM pathways. The general multi-risk DRM pathways propose a broad, system-level strategy to provide an integrated foundation for long-term resilience planning and therefore do not address a specific list of hazards. Hence, the measures included in the general multi-risk DRM pathways can be adapted further based on risk-specific priorities. The tailored cross sectoral DRM pathways, by contrast, are developed in response to specific risks with a focus on cascading and cross-sectoral impacts and specifically address the following sectors:

- Finance
- Infrastructure and transport
- Tourism
- Ecosystem and forestry

The UCPM PRAF has seven thematic areas including risk governance, risk assessment, risk management and planning, prevention, preparedness, response, and recovery and lessons learned. For each of these thematic areas, potential measures are identified. For example, in the theme *preparedness*, it includes 'improve the regional early warning system with a multi-risk approach'.

The cross-sectoral pathways focussed on two key cross-sectoral risks:

- Economic crisis and shortage of economic resources due to a downsizing tourism economy and declining agricultural product (Risk 1)
- Prolonged interruption of critical infrastructure and inefficient emergency response due to cascading impacts of consecutive disasters (Risk 2)

For these risks, more specific actions were identified, for example in the thematic area of risk governance, the pathway to allocate financial resources more effectively is achieved by encouraging the private sector to invest in infrastructure.

Pilot Leads discussed possibilities for future uptake of their approaches and results and identified opportunities to continue the collaboration with the participating stakeholders beyond the project. For instance, multi-risk indicators used in the Veneto Pilot to identify current and future risk hotspots supported the development of the first edition of the Regional Climate Change Adaptation Strategy (SRACC) in 2024 (Regione del Veneto, 2024) whereas more recent results obtained from the AI-based modelling (Dal Barco et al., 2025; Ferrario et al., 2024; Ferrario et al., 2025b; Nguyen et al., 2025) may inform its future updates.

3 Sectoral impacts and recommendations

Within MYRIAD-EU, six sectoral representatives were selected to ensure the scientific work remained relevant, to engage key stakeholders, and to support the dissemination of results within their respective sectors. The Infrastructure & Transport sector was represented by FEHRL (the Forum of European National Highway Research Laboratories). The Food and Agriculture sector was represented by CICYTEX, an agricultural research institute. The Ecosystem and Forestry sector was represented by Wetlands International, a global not-for-profit organisation dedicated to wetland conservation and restoration. The Energy sector was represented by TNO, an institute for applied research. The Finance sector was represented by AON, a reinsurance company. Finally, the Tourism sector was represented by HOTREC, the Association of Hotels, Restaurants & Cafés in Europe.

Each sector has produced a Sectoral Brief, outlining the key recommendations for their sectors based on the work carried out in MYRIAD-EU. In the following subsections, key aspects and recommendations from these briefs are summarised.

3.1 Infrastructure & Transport

Europe relies heavily on its transport infrastructure, however, this infrastructure is increasingly exposed to natural hazards such as floods, earthquakes, heatwaves, and storms. When these hazards cause damage, the impacts extend beyond direct losses, triggering significant economic consequences through indirect effects such as supply chain disruptions. To enhance the resilience of the Infrastructure & Transport sector to multi-hazard risks, the following recommendations are proposed (Adesiyun, 2025):

- **Integrated risk assessment models:** Develop and apply models that capture interdependencies and vulnerabilities across the transport network to better inform investment and adaptation decisions.
- **Cross-sectoral collaboration:** Strengthen coordination with other sectors to enable joint preparedness, planning, and response to extreme weather and multi-hazard events.
- **Real-time data sharing mechanisms:** Establish systems that facilitate the exchange of real-time information during hazard events, improving coordination, decision-making, and response speed.
- **Infrastructure resilience:** Prioritise the design, maintenance, and upgrading of critical assets (e.g., bridges, tunnels, and rail lines) to ensure they can withstand extreme weather and other natural hazards.

3.2 Food & Agriculture

The food & agriculture sector is highly vulnerable to multi-hazards such as extreme heat combined with droughts and flooding combined with landslides, which can severely impact food and water security. For instance, the 2022 drought led to significant declines in maize, soybean, and sunflower yields across Europe. Assessing single hazards in isolation can substantially underestimate the risk posed by compound events, such as a warm winter followed by a cold spring, which can damage crops during critical growth stages. To strengthen resilience, the sector brief recommends the following actions (Campillo & Gonzalo, 2025):

- **Governance and planning:** Integrate climate and soil indicators, as well as crop phenology, into agricultural and water management planning.
- **Tools, data, and modelling:** Apply composite heat-drought indices in crop models, combining sensors and satellite data for irrigation management, early warning, and systemic risk assessment.
- **Water and soil management:** Improve water-use efficiency and enhance infiltration and retention through green infrastructure and modernised irrigation systems.

- **Plant health and biodiversity:** Implement integrated pest management and promote the conservation of functional biodiversity.
- **Varieties and diversification:** Adapt crop varieties and calendars, diversify spatially and altitudinally, and explore opportunities such as agrovoltatics.
- **Economy and insurance:** Develop financial instruments that provide coverage for chain events, establish contingency funds, and train farmers in resilient agricultural practices.

3.3 Ecosystem & Forestry

Wetlands and other ecosystems are critical components for reducing disaster risk, providing natural protection against floods, droughts, and coastal erosion. However, as these systems degrade, vulnerability and risk increase, making it essential to prioritise the preservation of these nature-based solutions, especially in the face of climate change. Therefore, the ecosystem & forestry sector provides the following recommendations (Cordier & Appulo, 2025):

- **Cross-sectoral integration:** Wetlands and ecosystems link human activities, living conditions, and economic sectors. Embedding them in disaster risk reduction fosters collaboration across academia, policymakers, businesses, and public authorities, helping to overcome siloed approaches.
- **Integrate wetlands in multi-hazard risk management:** Recognise wetlands as essential infrastructure for disaster prevention, climate adaptation, and biodiversity protection, ensuring they are considered in multi-hazard planning.
- **Policy and governance:** Embed ecosystems into disaster risk frameworks and strengthen their representation in EU and national policies to unlock their full potential for resilient societies.

3.4 Energy

The European energy sector is currently undergoing a major transition to decarbonise and to mitigate further climate change. However, this transition faces growing challenges from interconnected risks, such as climate change impacts and geopolitical tensions, that threaten the resilience and stability of energy systems across Europe. Climate extremes, including sea level rise, heatwaves, and strong winds, can significantly affect the availability of primary energy sources. This is particularly critical as the share of renewable energy increases, given its sensitivity to changes in wind patterns and cloud cover, amongst others. Additionally, extreme conditions can disrupt the transformation, transmission, distribution, and storage of energy, as well as influence energy demand, especially during periods of extreme heat. In light of the MYRIAD-EU results, the energy sector recommends the following actions to strengthen resilience and adaptability (Bulder et al., 2025):

- **Modernise energy infrastructure:** upgrade energy infrastructure to withstand extreme multi-hazard events.
- **Extend cross-border interconnections:** enhance grid stability and energy security.
- **Improve data collection and analytics:** collect on infrastructure vulnerability and hazard exposure to support advanced risk assessment and informed decision-making.
- **Training and education:** train energy sector professions in multi-risk thinking, including compound and systemic risk scenarios.

3.5 Finance

Multi-hazards are a known risk in the finance sector. Flooding from hurricanes, flooding associated with windstorms, and hazards triggered by earthquakes are explicitly modelled. However, current risk models often treat these hazards as static, not accounting for climate change-driven increases in extreme events or the dynamic nature of vulnerability. Recent insurance losses, such as those caused by the triple storms Eunice, Dudley, and Franklin in the UK in 2022, highlight the importance

of incorporating multi-hazard risk into the (re-)insurance industry. Therefore, the finance sector has the following recommendations (Champion & Madappatt, 2025):

- **Model multi-hazards in catastrophe models:** Enable models to explicitly identify how each hazard (e.g., windstorms, floods) contributes to total risk, rather than treating hazards as independent or static.
- **Incorporate time-varying vulnerability:** Move beyond the assumption of static vulnerability by accounting for how exposure, vulnerability, and risk evolve over time, particularly under climate change.
- **Address cross-line risks:** Recognise that multi-hazards affect multiple insurance lines (property, business interruption, life) and improve understanding of the resulting interconnections to identify solutions that reduce cascading impacts.
- **Consider spatial and temporal dimensions of multi-risks:** Incorporate both where and when hazards occur into risk-diversification strategies to improve resilience and reduce correlated losses.
- **Differentiate impacts of multi-hazards in modelling:** Ensure catastrophe models distinguish between impacts arising from multiple hazards interacting, rather than aggregating them into single-hazard impacts.

3.6 Tourism

Tourism is a key economic sector, particularly in the Veneto and Canary Islands Pilot regions, where it contributes significantly to GDP. However, the sector faces growing risks from natural hazards, pandemics, and wildfires. Because tourism depends heavily on interconnected sectors such as transport and energy, it is essential to adopt a multi-risk perspective at the destination level. This approach enables better preparedness and ensures the safety of travellers in the face of compounding and cascading risks. Therefore, the tourism sector has the following recommendations (Khazai et al., 2025):

- **Mandate multi-hazard risk modelling for major tourism investments:** Require risk assessments that capture direct, indirect and cascading risks for all substantial tourism projects.
- **Adopt phased integration of MYRIAD-EU's six-step framework:** Embed the framework progressively into tourism policies, budgets and destination master plans to guide resilience planning.
- **Leverage public-private partnerships with incentives:** Use mechanisms such as tax credits and subsidised insurance to promote hazard-resilient infrastructure and sustainable practices in tourism.
- **Deploy observatories and dashboards to monitor risks and resilience metrics:** Set up transparent monitoring systems for tourism destinations, enhancing stakeholder trust and informed decision-making.
- **Promote regional and global scaling by replicating successful Pilots:** Scale up best practice Pilots (e.g., in the Canary Islands) and share successful approaches internationally to improve sector-wide resilience.
- **Strengthen financial protections for SMEs and workers:** Establish dedicated insurance schemes, relief funds and risk pools tailored to small tourism businesses and employees.
- **Integrate adaptive land-use and sustainability policies:** Ensure land-use planning and sustainability measures balance short-term recovery with long-term resilience and avoid maladaptation.

4 Early Career Research Board & Empowerment

Early Career Researchers (ECRs) played a central role in the MYRIAD-EU project, making up approximately 30% of the consortium. From the proposal phase, the project emphasised ECR empowerment, primarily through the Early Career Researcher Board (ECRB), which rotated every two years. The ECRB organised ECR-focused events, disseminated relevant information, and included an elected Early Career Representative as a full member of the project Management Team, enabling direct input into project decisions.

The large, interdisciplinary MYRIAD-EU consortium provided ECRs with repeated opportunities for mentorship and collaboration across sectors, supporting both professional development and research goals. Insights from ECRs and senior members informed a broader analysis identifying key mechanisms for empowerment (Schlumberger & De Polt et al., 2025), grouped into three categories: (1) structural involvement in project management; (2) organisation of ECR events; and (3) network-building beyond individual work. Three enabling factors were highlighted: (1) direct influence and advisory support, (2) ECR agency to act, and (3) contextual project factors.

Feedback from both internal and external stakeholders confirmed that ECR engagement was a major strength of MYRIAD-EU. The project demonstrates that embedding ECR empowerment into structure, activities, and networks delivers lasting benefits for both researchers and project outcomes.

5 Legacy & Outlook

The MYRIAD-EU project has developed a wide range of concepts, tools, and frameworks, many of which will continue to be used and maintained after the project ends. This includes, but is not limited to, the following outputs:

- The Disaster Risk Gateway
- The multi-risk concept into the update of the UNDRR/International Science Council Hazard Information Profiles (HIPs) (UNDRR/ISC, 2025)
- The MYRIAD-EU Framework
- The MYRIAD-EU Dashboard
- The Metadatabase for Dynamics of Risk Drivers
- The MYRIAD-EU Software

In addition to the above mentioned outputs, several other activities were undertaken in the project with long-term impact:

1. We co-organised the 3rd International Conference on Natural Hazards and Risks in a Changing World. Given the high quality and rich variation of the scientific contributions at this conference we submitted a journal article (Tiggeloven et al., 2025) in which we document the arc of the scientific discussions held at the conference, synthesise the main findings from sessions, and set out expert knowledge on how state-of-the-art science can fill gaps outlined by the Sendai Framework Mid Term Review.
2. We organised two policy workshops to disseminate the results of the MYRIAD-EU project and discuss policy implications with relevant policy makers such as the UNDRR and DG-ECHO. The key policy learnings of the first 1.5 years of the project are summarised in a policy brief (Ward et al., 2023), and a second policy brief (Cordier et al., 2025) sets out policy recommendations on how policy-makers, practitioners and authorities, from the local to the European Union's level, can take action now and include compounding hazards, risk cascades, and wildcard events into climate risk assessments. A recording of the second policy workshop, which was held at the end of the project, is openly available¹.
3. We contributed to the European Climate Risk Assessment (EUCRA) report which identifies key climate risks in Europe and suggests priorities for adapting policies. The report refers to the MYRIAD-EU's framework for multi-risk assessment as a systematic approach to managing risks.
4. We have collaborated, and continue to collaborate, with the Joint Research Centre on vulnerability dynamics associated with compound flood impacts across European regions (e.g. Ronco et al., 2025).
5. We continue to be a part of several working groups of RiskKAN (Knowledge Action Network on Emergent Risks and Extreme Events) and CMINE (The Crisis Management Innovation Network Europe) to continue and drive forward our understanding of cascading risk and disaster risk management.
6. We co-organised the DRR Academy for ECR's in 2024. The Academy brought together young researchers and practitioners to co-learn from each other about (multi-)risk. Due to its success, the academy will be held again in 2026.
7. We developed a digitalised version of the *Breaking the Silos* game, originally developed by de Ruiter et al. (2021). *Breaking the Silos* is a serious game designed to support various stakeholders (including policy makers, risk managers, researchers) in understanding and managing the complexities of DRR measures in a multi-risk (multi-hazard) setting, thereby

¹ <https://www.myriadproject.eu/newsmyriad/europe-faces-growing-interconnected-risks-myriad-eu-policy-roundtable-charts-the-way-forward/>

moving away from hazard-silo thinking. The game is available online at <https://bridging-the-silos.myriadproject.eu/> (Daneau et al., 2025).

Collectively, the project's activities and outputs, as well as progress made in other initiatives, have advanced the multi-risk field over the last five years. At the same time, they highlight new challenges and research avenues that call for further development. A scientific synthesis of the MYRIAD-EU project has been published as a perspective paper by Ward et al. (2025). In this paper, we also reflect on potential future research avenues, building from our experiences over the course of the MYRIAD-EU project. These avenues are briefly listed below:

- To continue the mainstreaming and mutual understanding of concepts and definitions.
- To continue developing a strong evidence base of how multi-hazard-risk both shapes, and is shaped by, risk dynamics over space and time.
- To further develop methods for providing both current and future multi-(hazard)-risk scenarios.
- To further integrate and improve the usability, accessibility, and interoperability of multi-risk assessment tools to evaluate DRM options
- To more explicitly include equity into multi-risk assessment and adaptation by addressing social vulnerability, fair participation, and the needs of marginalised groups.
- To continue extensively testing and coproducing multi-(hazard)-risk knowledge in in-depth case studies to ensure the transferability and scalability beyond isolated case studies or Pilot region.
- To examine how the multi-(hazard)-risk tools, methods, and knowledge developed can support the development of Multi-Hazard Early Warning Systems (MHEWS).
- To further strengthen opportunities for ECR leadership and empowerment within project structures.
- Together, these avenues outline a forward-looking agenda that will continue to advance multi-risk research and impact beyond the MYRIAD-EU project.

6 References

- Adesiyun, A. (2025). Sectoral Brief: Addressing multi-hazard risk in the transport and infrastructure sector - learnings from the MYRIAD-EU project. MYRIAD-EU Sectoral Brief. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17787359>
- British Geological Survey. (2025). Online repository of storylines on multi- risk decision- making. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16366883>
- Brookes, S., Cabascia, E., Pietruczuk, A., Hochrainer-Stigler, S. (2025). Dashboard report. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16366458>
- Buijs, S. L., Sauer, I. J., Kropf, C. M., Juhel, S., Stalhandske, Z., De Ruiter, M.C. (2025). Recovery under consecutive disasters: how recovery dynamics shape societal resilience. EGU sphere [pre-print]. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2025-3200>
- Bulder, B., Wiggelinkhuizen, E., Nair, J.M. (2025). Sectoral Brief: Addressing multi-hazard risk in the energy sector - learnings from the MYRIAD-EU project. MYRIAD-EU Sectoral Brief. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17947317>
- Campillo, C., Gonzalo, J. (2025). Sectoral Brief: Addressing multi-hazard risk in the food and agriculture sector - learnings from the MYRIAD-EU project. MYRIAD-EU Sectoral Brief. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17787170>
- Casartelli, V., Salpina, D., Marengo, A., Vivo, G., Sørensen, J.H., Mysiak, J. (2025a). An innovative framework to conduct peer reviews of disaster risk management capabilities under the Union Civil Protection Mechanism (UCPM). *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 120, 105350. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2025.105350>
- Casartelli, V., Salpina, D., Marengo, A., Mohammadi, S. (2025b). Vaia 2018 - Plausible Vaia 2074 storm: Storylines for the Veneto Pilot. Myriad-EU project, ArcGIS StoryMaps. <https://doi.org/10.25424/cmcc-b5tt-1x90>
- Casartelli, V., Salpina, D., Marengo, A., Ferrario, D.M., Mysiak, J., Torresan, S. (submitted). Back to the Future: a mixed-methods approach for developing event-based participatory storylines to advance climate risk assessments. Submitted to *Climate Risk Management*
- Champion, A., Madappatt, N. (2025). Sectoral Brief: Addressing multi-hazard risk in the finance sector - learnings from the MYRIAD-EU project. MYRIAD-EU Sectoral Brief. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17787018>
- Ciurean, R.L. (2025). Reflections on stakeholder engagement, co-production methods, and knowledge co-development in the MYRIAD-EU project. doi:10.5194/egusphere-egu25-21264
- Claassen, J.N., Ward, P.J., Daniell, J., Koks, E.E., Tiggeloven, T., de Ruiter, M.C. (2023). A new method to compile global multi-hazard event sets. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-40400-5>
- Claassen, J.N., Koks, E.E., de Ruiter, M.C., Ward, P.J., Jäger, W. (2024). VineCopulas: an open-source Python package for vine copula modelling. *Journal of Open Source Software*, 9, 6728. <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.06728>
- Cocuccioni, S., Pittore, M., Zebisch, M., Schneiderbauer, S., Shepherd, T. G., Casartelli, V., Crummy, J., Pedde, S. (2025). Risk Storylines: A Community-Led Discussion between Disaster and Climate Science. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 106(8), E1717–E1723. <https://doi.org/10.1175/bams-d-25-0155.1>
- Cordier, E., Appulo, L. (2025). Sectoral Brief: Addressing linkages between multi-hazard risk and wetlands ecosystems - learnings from the MYRIAD-EU project. MYRIAD-EU Sectoral Brief. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17947278>
- Crummy, J., Banks, V., Ciurean, R., Duncan, M., Smale, L., Daloz, A. S., Ma, L., Casartelli, V., Torresan, S., Stuparu, D., Tatman, S., Geurts, D., Rautenbach, S., Warren, A., Toebrock, L., Šakić Trogrlić, R., Hochrainer-Stigler, S., Padrón Fumero, N., García González, S., & Díaz Pacheco, J.

- (2025). Online repository of storylines on multi-risk decision-making. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16366883>
- Dal Barco, M.K., Maraschini, M., Ferrario, D.M., Nguyen, N.D., Torresan, S., Vascon, S., Critto, A. (2024). A machine learning approach to evaluate coastal risks related to extreme weather events in the Veneto region (Italy). *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 108, 104526. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2024.104526>
- Dal Barco, M.K., Maraschini, M., Nguyen, N.D., Ferrario, D.M., Rufo, O., Fonseca, H.L., Vascon, S., Torresan, S., Critto, A. (2025). Integrating AI and climate change scenarios for multi-risk assessment in the coastal municipalities of the Veneto region. *Science of The Total Environment*, 965, 178586. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2025.178586>
- Daneau, J., de Ruiter, M., van Maanen, N., Cabascia, E., Turetta, G., Pietruczuk, A. (2025). *D7.4 Serious game*. MYRIAD-EU Project Deliverable. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16366986>
- Daniell, J., Blanz, B., Girard, T., Khazai, B., Schaefer, A., Brand, J., Maier, A., Claassen, J., Strelkovski, N., Sillmann, J., García, M., Padrón, N., Ma, L. (2024). Final report on methods for generating hazard event sets and quantifying risk. MYRIAD-EU Project Deliverable. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16365994>
- Daniell, J., Schaefer, A., Khazai, B., Girard, T., Brand, J., Maier, A., Michalke, S., Blanz, B., Claassen, J., Strelkovskii, N., Raj, S. (2025). *Software package and user guide for multi-hazard and multi-risk scenario generation*. MYRIAD-EU Project Deliverable. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16366801>
- De Polt, K., Ward, P.J., de Ruiter, M., Bogdanovich, E., Reichstein, M., Frank, D., and Orth, R. (2023). Quantifying impact-relevant heatwave durations. *Environmental Research Letters*, 18, 104005, doi:10.1088/1748-9326/acf05e
- De Polt, K., Dormann, C.F., Ward, P.J., Ruiter, M.C., Runkle, J.D., Wutzler, T., Reichstein, M., Orth, R. (2025). Regional Differences in the Impact of Heat and Moisture on Public Health within Europe. *ESS Open Archive* [pre-print]. <https://doi.org/10.22541/essoar.174282873.38972040/v1>
- de Ruiter, M. C., Couasnon, A., Ward, P.J. (2021). Breaking the Silos: an online serious game for multi-risk disaster risk reduction (DRR) management. *Geoscience Communication*, 4, 383-397. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gc-4-383-2021>
- de Ruiter, M. C., van Loon, A. F. (2022). The challenges of dynamic vulnerability and how to assess it. *iScience*, 25, 104720. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2022.104720>
- Ducros, G., Tiggeloven, T., Ma, L., Daloz, A.S., Schuhen, N., Claassen, J., de Ruiter, M.C. (2025). Multi-hazards in Scandinavia: impacts and risks from compound heatwaves, droughts and wildfires. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 25, 4693–4712. doi:10.5194/nhess-25-4693-2025
- Duncan, M., Smale, L., Crummy, J., Ciurean, R., Napier, A., Chintham, S., Shelley, W., Gill, J., Schlumberger, J., Stuparu, D., Khazai, B., Girard, T., de Ruiter, M., Tiggeloven, T., Harris, R., Ferrario, D., Mysiak, J., Torresan, S., Claassen, J., Dai, R., Hochrainer-Stigler, S., Šakić Trogrlić, R., Sillman, J., Daniell, J. (2022). WIKI-style online crowdsourcing platform of multi-hazard, multi-risk methods, models, and tools. MYRIAD-EU Project Deliverable. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7327776>
- Ferrario, D. M., Tiggeloven T., Maraschini, M., Sano, M., Claassen, J., de Ruiter, M.C. , Torresan, S., Critto, A. (2025a). A machine learning methodology to identify current and future multi-hazard extreme events. *ESS Open Archive* [pre-print], <https://doi.org/10.22541/essoar.175396232.24844978/v1>, 2025a
- Ferrario, D.M., Tiggeloven, T., Casagrande, S., Sanò, M., de Ruiter, M.C., Critto, A., Torresan, S., 2025b (2025b). An AI approach for multi-risk assessment in the Veneto Region. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu25-16640>, 2025b
- Ferrario, D.M., Sanò, M., Maraschini, M., Critto, A., Torresan, S. (2025c). Review article: Harnessing Machine Learning methods for climate multi-hazard and multi-risk assessment, *EGUsphere* [pre-print]. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2025-670>, 2025c

Gill, J., Duncan, M., Ciurean, R., Smale, L., Stuparu, D., Schlumberger, J., ..., Ward, P.J. (2022). Handbook of Multi-Hazard, Multi-Risk Definitions and Concepts. MYRIAD-EU Project Deliverable. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7135138>

Gill, J.C., Duncan, M., de Ruiter, M., Tiggeloven, T., Ward, P.J., Smale, L., Ciurean, R. (2025). Concept note: The multi-hazard context and its relevance to the UN Office for Disaster Risk Reduction / International Science Council's Hazard Information Profiles (HIPs).. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15574444>

Gottardo, S., Ciurean, R., Daloz, A.S., Padron-Fumero, N., Šakić Trogrlić, R., Tatman, S., Torresan, S., Casartelli, V., Critto, A., Dal Barco, M.K., Díaz- Pacheco, J., Ferrario, D.M., García González, S., Gatti, I., Geurts, D., Hochrainer-Stigler, S., Ma, L., Marengo, A., Romero Manrique Lara, D., ... Ward, P.J. (2025). Final report on forward-looking DRM pathways and recommendations for upscaling and transferability. MYRIAD-EU Project Deliverable. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17245464>

Haasnoot, M., Kwakkel, J.H., Walker, W.E., Ter Maat, J. (2013). Dynamic adaptive policy pathways: A method for crafting robust decisions for a deeply uncertain world. *Global environmental change*, 23, 485-498. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2012.12.006>

Hochrainer-Stigler, S., Sakic Trogrlic, R., Reiter, K. (2022). Initial framework and guidance protocol document. MYRIAD-EU Project Deliverable. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7215816>

Hochrainer-Stigler, S., Trogrlić Šakić, R., Reiter, K., Ward, P.J., de Ruiter, M.C., Duncan, M.J., ... Gottardo, S. (2023). Toward a framework for systemic multi-hazard and multi-risk assessment and management. *iScience*, 26, 106736. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2023.106736>

Hochrainer-Stigler et al. (2026) Operationalizing Systemic Multi Hazard and Multi Risk Assessment: Lessons from the MYRIAD-EU Framework, in review.

IPCC (2022). Annex II: Glossary [Möller, V, J.B.R. Matthews, R. van Diemen, C. Méndez, S. Semenov, J.S. Fuglestedt, A. Reisinger (eds.)]. In: *Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* [H.-O. Pörtner, D.C. Roberts, M. Tignor, E.S. Poloczanska, K. Mintenbeck, A. Alegría, M. Craig, S. Langsdorf, S. Löschke, V.

Jäger, W.S., de Ruiter, M.C., Tiggeloven, T., Ward, P.J. (2025). What can we learn about multi-hazard impacts from global disaster records?, *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 25, 2751-2769, <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-25-2751-2025>

Khazai, B., Padrón Fumero, N., Machado, M. (2025). Sectoral Brief: Enhancing Tourism Destination Resilience: Insights of the MYRIAD-EU Multi-risk Approach. MYRIAD-EU Sectoral Brief.. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17787282>

Mysiak, J., Casartelli, V., Torresan, S. (2021). Union Civil Protection Mechanism – Peer Review Programme for disaster risk management: Assessment Framework. <https://civilprotection-knowledge-network.europa.eu/system/files/2024-07/the-analyticalassessment-framework-for-a-peer-review.pdf>

Ngoc Nguyen, D., Furlanetto, J., Critto, A., Torresan, S. (2025). Understanding multi-hazard risk dynamics between land use, climate extremes and water quality leveraging artificial intelligence. *Ecological Indicators*, 182, 114494, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2025.114494>

Regione del Veneto (2024). Strategia Regionale di Adattamento ai Cambiamenti Climatici. Documento preliminare. Allegato A. DGR n. 459 del 02 maggio 2024. Retrieved from <https://www.regione.veneto.it/web/ambiente-e-territorio/documento-preliminare>.

Ronco, M., Tilloy, A., Corbane, C., Feyen, L., Paprotny, D., Jager, W., Ward, P.J. (2025). Exploring vulnerability dynamics associated with compound flood impacts across European regions. doi:10.5194/egusphere-egu25-19024

Schlumberger, J., Stuparu, D., Ciurean, R.L., Duncan, M., Mysiak, J., Khazai, B., Rimmer, J., Dochiu, C., & Claassen, J. (2022a). Report on policies, policy-making processes, and governance for multi-

hazard, multi-risk management. MYRIAD-EU Project Deliverable.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7096835>

Schlumberger, J., Haasnoot, M., Aerts, J., de Ruiter, M. (2022b). Proposing DAPP-MR as a disaster risk management pathways framework for complex, dynamic multi-risk. *iScience*, 25, 105219. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2022.105219>

Schlumberger, J., Haasnoot, M., Aerts, J.C.J.H., Bril, V., van der Weide, L., de Ruiter, M. (2024). Evaluating Adaptation Pathways in a Complex Multi-Risk System. *Earth's Future*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2023ef004288>

Schlumberger, J., Stolte, T., Garcia, H.M., Sebastian, A., Jäger, W., Ward, P.J., de Ruiter, M., Šakić Trogrlić, R., Tijssen, A., de Brito, M. M. (2025a). Review article: Stocktaking of methods for assessing dynamic vulnerability in the context of flood hazard research. *EGUsphere* [pre-print] <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2025-850>

Schlumberger, J., Warren, A., Daloz, A. S., Geurts, D., Hochrainer-Stigler, S., Ma, L., Padrón-Fumero, N., Reiter, K., Trogrlić, R.Š., Tatman, S., Banks, V., Crummy, J., Díaz-Pacheco, J., Antequera, P.D., García-González, S., López-Díez, A., Arévalo, T.L.F., Romero-Manrique, D., Strelkovskii, N., ... de Ruiter, M.C. (2025b). Developing multi-risk DRM pathways - Lessons from four European case studies. *Climate Risk Management*, 50, 100753. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crm.2025.100753>

Schlumberger, J., Šakić Trogrlić, R., Aerts, J.C.J.H., Hyun, J.-H., Hochrainer-Stigler, S., de Ruiter, M., Haasnoot, M. (2025c). A pathways analysis dashboard prototype for multi-risk systems. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 25, 4089-4113. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-25-4089-2025>

Schlumberger, J., De Polt, K., Claassen, J.N., Tiggeloven, T., Buijs, S.L., de Ruiter, M. C., Gargiulo, M.V., Gill, J.C., Pantaleoni Reluy, N., Šakić Trogrlić, R., Ward, P. J. (2025). Empowering ECRs to make research projects flourish: lessons from a European research project. *Open Research Europe*, 5, 312. <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.21517.1>

Schaefer, A.M., Daniell, J.E., Khazai, B., Girard, T. (2022). Stochastic and Empirical Multi-Hazard Event Sets for Europe: Earthquake Stochastic Event Set for Europe (ISO3166 code) (Version V1) [Data set]. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7141934>

Shepherd, T.G., Boyd, E., Calel, R.A. (2018). Storylines: an alternative approach to representing uncertainty in physical aspects of climate change. *Climatic Change*, 151, 555-571, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-018-2317-9>

Sillmann, J., Shepherd, T. G., van den Hurk, B., Hazeleger, W., Martius, O., Slingo, J., Zscheischler, J. (2021). Event-Based Storylines to Address Climate Risk. *Earth's Future*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020ef001783>

Stolte, T.R., Koks, E.E., de Moel, H., Reimann, L., van Vliet, J., de Ruiter, M.C., & Ward, P.J. (2024). VulneraCity – drivers and dynamics of urban vulnerability based on a global systematic literature review. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 108, 104535. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2024.104535>

Stolte, T., Jäger, W., Daniell, J., Ward, P.J., Ruiter, de, M., Tiggeloven, T., De Polt, K., Buijs, S. L., Claassen, J., van Maanen, N., Sestito, B., Benito Lazaro, I., Ferrario, D.M., Nguyen, N.D., Dal Barco, M.K., Schlumberger, J., Torresan, S., Orth, R., Duncan, M., Smale, L. (2025a). Metadatabase for Dynamics of Risk Drivers (v1.1.0) [Data set]. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15553940>

Stolte, T., Jäger, W., Daniell, J., Ward, P., Ruiter, de, M., Tiggeloven, T., De Polt, K., Buijs, S.L., Claassen, J., van Maanen, N., Sestito, B., Benito Lazaro, I., Ferrario, D.M., Nguyen, N.D., Schlumberger, J., Torresan, S., Orth, R., Duncan, M., & Smale, L. (2025b). D4.5 Online database of empirical evidence of dynamics and feedbacks of risk drivers (Version V2). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16794440>

Tiggeloven, T., Stolte, T., Claassen, J., Chang, C.-W., Paszkowski, A., Schneiderbauer, S., Yotsui, S., Van Maanen, N. (2025a). Multi-hazards in an unequal world. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu25-1005>

UNDRR / ISC), 2025. Update of the UNDRR-ISC Hazard Information Profiles. Geneva, Switzerland, United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction, Paris, France, International Science Council

van Maanen, N., de Ruiter, M., Jäger, W., Casartelli, V., Ciurean, R., Padron, N., Daloz, A.S., Geurts, D., Gottardo, S., Hochrainer-Stigler, S., López Díez, A., Díaz Pacheco, J., Dorta Antequera, P., Febles Arévalo, T., García González, S., Hernández-Martín, R., Alvarez-Albelo, C., Diaz-Hernandez, J.J., Ma, L., ... Ward, P.J. (2025). Bridging Science and Practice on Multi-Hazard Risk Drivers: Stakeholder Insights from Five Pilot Studies in Europe. EGU sphere [pre-print]. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2025-3075>

Ward, P.J., Daniell, J., Duncan, M., Dunne, A., Hananel, C., Hochrainer-Stigler, S., ... de Ruiter, M.C. (2022). Invited perspectives: A research agenda towards disaster risk management pathways in multi-(hazard-)risk assessment. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 22, 1487-1497. doi:10.5194/nhess-22-1487-2022

Ward, P., Hochrainer-Stigler, S., Šakić Trogrlić, R., Machado, M., Ciurean, R., de Ruiter, M., Mysiak, J., Champion, A., Tiggeloven, T., Zheng, M., & Appulo, L. (2023). Reducing Risks Together: a systemic approach to reducing disaster risk in Europe. MYRIAD-EU First Policy Brief. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117905>

Cordier, C., Appulo, L., Ward, P.J. (2025). Policy Brief: Integrating Multi-Hazard Risk Management Approach into Key EU Policies. MYRIAD-EU First Policy Brief. <https://zenodo.org/records/17998322>

Ward, P.J., Buijs, S., Ciurean, R., Claassen, J., Daniell, J., De Polt, K., Duncan, M., Gottardo, S., Hochrainer-Stigler, S., Šakić Trogrlić, R., Schlumberger, J., Tiggeloven, T., Torresan, S., van Maanen, N., Warren, A., Álvarez-Albelo, C.D., Banks, V., Blanz, B., Casartelli, V., Correa González, J., Crummy, J., Daloz, A.S., de Ruiter, M.C., Díaz-Hernández, J.J., Díaz-Pacheco, J., Dorta Antequera, P., Ferrario, D., García-González, S., Gill, J., Hernández-Martín, R., Jäger, W., López-Díez, A., Ma, L., Mysiak, J., Ngoc Nguyen, D., Padrón Fumero, N., Petrescu, E.-C., Reiter, K., Sillmann, J., Smale, L. (2025). Reducing Risk Together: moving towards a more holistic approach to multi-(hazard-)risk assessment and management, EGU sphere [preprint] <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2025-5897>

Warren, A., Stuparu, D., Schlumberger, J., Tijssen, A., Dochiu, C., Rimmer, J. (2023). Guidance document for Pilots on collaborative systems analysis approaches. MYRIAD-EU Project Deliverable. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10082460>

Appendix 1

Table 1: Acronyms and names of MYRIAD-EU partner institutes

Acronym	Full name
VUA	Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (Stichting VU)
UKRI BGS	British Geological Survey (UK Research and Innovation)
CMCC	Fondazione Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici
DRES	Stichting Deltares
Risklayer	Risklayer GmbH
IIASA	International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis
Arctik	Arctik SRL
CICERO	CICERO Center for International Climate Research
ULL	Universidad de La Laguna
MPG	Max Planck Institute for Biogeochemistry (Max-Planck-Gesellschaft)
ASE	Bucharest University of Economic Studies (Academia de Studii Economice din București)
FEHRL	Forum of European National Highway Research Laboratories
WIEA	Wetlands International – European Association
HOTREC	HORTEC: Hotels, Restaurants & Cafés in Europe
CICYTEX	Centro de Investigaciones Científicas y Tecnológicas de Extremadura
AON	AON UK Limited
TNO	Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research
UHAM	University of Hamburg
UNIVE	Ca' Foscari University Venice

